

The Badoh-Pathari Saptamātrkā Inscription

Dániel Balogh, British Museum

high-resolution images: <https://zenodo.org/record/1306902> (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1306902)

[1](s)iddhaM(+|)

<Verse 1. Metre: vasantatilaka>

p(r)āvṛtya yaḥ (sa)-rudhiram gaja-carmma r(au)dra[m]
pr[e]tālaye niśi mahoraga-k[o](ṣṭha)-(sūt)(ra)[ḥ]
(?n)[?ātyaṅ ka] (r)[?o](?ti śiva)-(mā)tr-gaṅ(?ānuyāt)[?o]
(r)[ud](r)[o jaya]^[2](ty ama)ra-vand(i)ta-pāda-yugmaḥ

<Verse 2. Metre: vasantatilaka>

tasy(ā)nu bha(kta-ja)na-nitya-hito (+')nukampī
(vī)(r)(?ār)[?bhak](o) ja(yat)i (?mātr)-ga(ṅ)(?ais sa)(nā)(?tha)ḥ
ya(?f) (pūjyate sata)tam (?o) [---] ^[3](r)
(ijyāṃjali)-praṇava-(baly-u)pahāra-yogaiḥ

<Verse 3. Metre: mandākrāntā>

(br)[ā](hmyā)(?dīkās s)(va)-(?mata-gatayo) (yā)ś ca(ra)(+ṃ)t(y u)g[r](a)[-] ^[4]
(rudra)-kṣ(et)r(e) sah(a) (?vi)(ca)ritu(m yā)(?f) (prah)ṛ(ṣṭa-pra)(?ṅitāḥ)
[4](?yāsām ta)(tv)(?a)(n na) (+ca) vicarit(a)ṃ jñāyate jñāna-(v)i(d)bhi(ḥ)
(?k)ā(?lo d)eśo (h/p)i [---] (?n)i (?ya)(t)(?o) (?yo paro he)[-] ^[5]

<Verse 4. Metre: sragdharā>

yā(s)ā(?m) [?ārtt](?o balau)(ghair vva)la(bhi)-(?-vihara)[?ṅe] ^[5](?siddha)-(gandharvva)-
va(+r)(g)(?g)aḥ
(?vā)yur yy(ā) sām jave(na druta)(?-ratha-tarasā) [-] ^[6]
[-----] ^[6]mātaras tās satata-sumanaso mātrva(n) mā(m a)vantu(l)

(dharmma-vi)[ja](yino mahārā)[ja]-(śr)[ī]-(?ku)[mā](?ra)[?gupta]-(?rājye) [?20] [?āśā]^[7](?ḍha)-śukla-
divase trayodaśyām bhagavatyo mātaraḥ (pratiṣṭh)(?ā)[?2](?tosa) [?1] (?sā) [?2] (?rava) [?1] (?śyasya)
[?28] ^[8](kr)(?tsnā)(vam)ukta-viṣayeśvarasya mahārāja-ja(yatsenas)ya (satputreṇa sa)(?jana)s(?svajana-
pura) [?30] ^[9](śīl)(?ena daivata-dvijāti)-[dha]r(mma)-guru-bhak[t]e(?na) [?45]^[10][...]